

**PRODUCT QUALITY AND COMPETITIVENESS
THE ROLE OF METROLOGY AND STANDARDIZATION IN
ENSURING.**

HAMIDOV ABDULAZIZ JAXONGIR OGLI

Jizzakh Polytechnic institute, student,

Phone Number: +998885232303; abdulazizhamidov549@gmail.com

BADALOV NOMOZ JURABOYEVICH

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute, associate professor,

phone: +998903110662; nomozbadalov@gmail.com

Orcid: 0000-0003-3392-9150

Abstract: As a result of the implementation of the quality management system, enterprises increase the volume of product production, achieve an increase in labor productivity, reduce the costs of quality improvement, and increase their competitiveness. Everywhere, requirements for the quality of activity in any field are regulated by regulatory documents. Standardization, metrology, and certification based on the widespread use of international standards are aimed at ensuring product quality and increasing competitiveness. Quality as a factor of competitiveness extends to the entire national economy.

Keywords: product, quality, standard, competition, system, standardization, metrology, quality system, regulatory document, quality management, regulation, quality indicators.

Everywhere, the requirements for the quality of activity in any field are regulated by regulatory documents, in which it is envisaged to solve not only existing but also future tasks, that is, to meet not only the established but also future needs. Mankind has been trying to understand the nature of quality for many centuries. Philosophical and scientific-technical definition of quality has their history [1]. The

ancient Greek philosopher Aristotle (384-322 BC) believed that "a quality consists of a set of specific properties that distinguish this object from other objects." The English philosopher John Locke (Locke) (1632-1704) thought that "the main properties objectively characteristic of an object, such as size, shape, mass, etc., constitute quality [2]." German philosopher Hegel (Hegel) Georg Wilhelm Friedrich (1770-1831) stated that "quality is something that is a thing because of its quality, and if it loses its quality, it ceases to be a thing. " The earliest records of quality control in the United States date back to 1924 [3]. At that time, the American scientist Walter Schuhart from the laboratory of the Bell Telephone Company for the first time used a statistical control chart to analyze the quality of an industrial product. But the philosophical definition of quality could not satisfy the need for a scientific and technical definition of quality. In 1968, a group of scientists analyzed hundreds of works on this problem and as a result proposed their terms and concepts, which became the basis of GOST 15467 terms in the field of product quality. "Quality is a set of product properties that ensure its suitability to meet certain needs by the purposes for which it is intended [4]." Armand Feigenbaum, an American expert on quality problems, in his book "Product Quality Control," shows the range of issues related to the concept of "quality" in the modern conditions of production and consumption and says that "In a situation where the range of manufactured products is constantly expanding, the consumer, whether he is a housewife, whether it is an industrial corporation, a chain of department stores or the Ministry of Defense, the main factor that determines the feasibility of purchasing a product is the quality of the product [5]. Complex systems of product quality management, which are carefully designed and efficiently operated, ensure the company's profitability and considerable profit. As a result of the implementation of the quality management system, enterprises increase the volume of product production, achieve an increase in labor productivity, significantly reduce the costs of quality improvement, and increase their competitiveness [6].

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, in 1998, the term "Quality" was adopted in the state standard of Uzbekistan Uz Dst 8402, which states: "Quality is a set of descriptions related to the ability of the object to meet the specified and expected needs ." It should be noted that the activity

of almost every employee working in the organization, regardless of which department he works in and at what level, to one degree or another affects the quality of the labor product created by the enterprise and its competitiveness [7]. This determines the modern view of production management as its competitiveness and the competitiveness of the product it produces, that is, as quality management. This approach forms the basis of the modern quality management system's advanced concept of total quality management. In Uzbekistan, as in many countries of the world, ISO standards of the 9000 series were accepted as national standards. They consist of general requirements aimed at the quality management system of organizations in various industry and economy sectors [8]. These standards were developed by summarizing the existing experience in the field of creating a quality management system of countries that have transitioned to a market economy and are intended for any organization. However, the requirements regulated in the standards refer to abstract economic mechanisms and consist of general information, for the understanding of which relevant knowledge and work experience in market conditions or the help of quality system specialists was necessary [9]. Standardization, metrology, certification, and improvement of related fields, ensuring product quality and increasing competitiveness based on the wide application of international standards. Eight principles of quality management These eight principles of quality management, which are the basis for increasing the performance of the organization, are based on the international standard ISO 9000:

Work to adapt to the first consumer. An organization depends on its customers and therefore needs to understand the customer's day-to-day and future needs, meet their requirements, and strive to exceed the customer's expectations while doing so [10].

The leadership of the second leadership. Leaders determine the directions and goals of the organization's activities. They create an environment in which people are fully engaged in achieving the organization's goals. Their tasks are to define quality policy and goals in the field of quality for the organization, to ensure that relevant processes are introduced and to enable them to fulfill the customer's requirements, to determine and implement an effective quality management system, and to ensure that it is used to achieve these goals, to ensure that the necessary resources are available, and to determine the results achieved. comparison with

goals, making decisions on quality policy and goals in the field of quality and making decisions on actions to be taken to improve quality [11].

The third is to attract people. Employees at all levels are the essence of the organization, and fully engaging them allows them to use their skills for the organization's benefit [12].

Fourthly, a reasonable approach. The expected result is achieved more effectively when appropriate resources and activities are managed as a process. A process approach supports an organization's ability to define and understand its activities and interactions. It enables the organization to identify, manage and control these processes. Any type of activity or set of activities that uses control mechanisms to transform inputs into outputs is called a process. Input elements, control, and output elements can be tangible and intangible. Output elements of one process can be input elements for another [13].

Fifth, a systemic approach to management is the identification, understanding, and management of a system of interrelated processes toward defined goals that contribute to the organization's achievement of good results and efficiency [14].

The sixth constant is to go well. Continuous improvement is an unchanging goal of the organization. Continuous improvement refers to actions taken to improve product properties and specifications or the efficiency and effectiveness of the processes used to produce and deliver them. The cycle of the improvement process may include: identifying, measuring, and analyzing the current situation, setting goals for improvement, searching for possible solutions, evaluating these solutions, implementing the selected solutions, measuring the results of the implementation, validating, analyzing, and evaluating, formalizing the changes. Improvements will be permanent and will not be considered in terms of the final solutions provided. Results may be reviewed as necessary to identify opportunities for improvement. Audits, customer feedback, and quality management system reviews can also identify opportunities for improvement [15].

A seventh fact-based decision-making approach. Effective decision-making is based on logical and intuitive analysis of data and information.

The eighth product is mutually beneficial relationships with suppliers. A mutually beneficial relationship between an organization and its product suppliers enhances the wealth-

creation capabilities of both organizations. The method of introducing the quality management system introduced in the organization based on the ISO 9000 standard consists of the following several stages: defining the goals and quality policy of the organization in the field of quality, determining the decisive processes for achieving the quality goals, and determining the measurements to determine the effectiveness of each process aimed at achieving the quality goals, applying these measurements to determine the effectiveness of each process, identify ways to prevent defects, reduce variability and minimize defects and waste, seek opportunities to reduce risks and improve the productivity and efficiency of processes, identify improvements that can provide the best results with the least risk, and importance level deployment, planning strategies, processes and resources to achieve identified improvements, executing plans, monitoring the results of improvements, results obtained, expected results is to review improvement actions to identify appropriate corrective actions [16].

The interaction of standardization, like the interaction of scientific and technical activities and the concept of quality, is derived from the concepts of these terms accepted by the International Organization for Standardization as a set of object descriptions:

A standard is a document developed based on agreement and approved by a recognized body, in which rules, general principles, or descriptions related to various types of activities or their results are established for general and multiple uses, and it is directed to achieve a reasonable level of regulation in a particular field. Standardization is an activity aimed at achieving a reasonable level of regulation in a specific field using establishing rules for general and multiple uses concerning existing or potential tasks. Standardization object Objects that need to be standardized [17]. A regulatory document is a document that defines the descriptions, general principles, and rules related to various types of activities or their results. Quality is the degree of compliance of its set of specifications with the requirements, that is, a set of specifications related to the ability of the object to meet the specified or expected needs. Quality is a set of properties and characteristics of products or processes that ensure their suitability for use for their intended purpose.

References:

1. O'g B. O. N. et al. The role of quality management system in increasing product quality in enterprises //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 12. – С. 228-233.
2. Бадалов Н. Ж., Бердимуродов Г. Т., Бадалов У. Н. СИФАТЛИ МАХСУЛОТ ИШЛАБ ЧИҚАРИЛИШИДА СИНОВ ВА ЎЛЧОВЛАРНИНГ АХАМИЯТИ //IJTIMOIY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMIIY JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 101-106.
3. Бадалов Н. Ж., Бадалов У. Н. КОРХОНАЛАРДА МАҲСУЛОТЛАР СИФАТИНИ БОШҚАРИШНИНГ АСОСИЙ ФУНКЦИЯЛАРИ //Academic research in modern science. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 38-45.
4. Juraboyevich B. N. et al. Development Of Metrology And The Role And Importance Of Metrological Supply In Enterprises //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2022. – Т. 4. – С. 136-139.
5. Juraboyevich B. N., Son B. O. N. THE ROLE OF QUALITY PRODUCTION IN ENTERPRISES //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 9. – №. 10. – С. 644-647.
6. Jo'raboevich B. N., Ikramovich I. D., Nomozovich B. U. SINOV VA KALIBRLASH LABORATORIYALARIDA KOMPETENTLIGINI XALQARO DARAJADA OSHIRISH OMILLARI //E Conference Zone. – 2022. – С. 128-131.
7. Бадалов Н. Ж., Икромов Д. И., Бадалов У. Н. КОРХОНАЛАРДА ЎЛЧАШЛАР, СИНОВЛАР ВА ТАҲЛИЛЛАРНИНГ МЕТРОЛОГИК АХАМИЯТИ //Международная конференция академических наук. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 15. – С. 11-17.
8. Jo'raboevich B. N., Ikramovich I. D., Nomozovich B. U. SIFAT MENEJMENT TIZIMINING-SINOV VA KALIBRLASH LABORATORIYALARIDAGI O'RNI //E Conference Zone. – 2022. – С. 67-71.
9. BADALOV U. N. O. QUALITY IN PRODUCT QUALITY MANAGEMENT SIGNIFICANCE OF INDICATORS //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC

- CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION". – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 65-75.
- 10.**BADALOV U. N. O. THE IMPORTANCE OF TESTING LABORATORIES AND THEIR ACCREDITATION //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION". – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 2. – C. 163-169.
- 11.**Juraboevich B. N. Products in Manufacturing Enterprises the Essence of Quality Management //International Journal of Development and Public Policy. – 2021. – T. 1. – №. 5. – C. 117-118.
- 12.**Jo‘raboevich B. N. QUALITY EXPORT PRODUCTS IN ENTERPRISES GENERAL AND SPECIAL IN PRODUCTION IMPORTANCE OF REGULATIONS //ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 6. – C. 1-7.
- 13.**Jo‘raboyevich B. N. ROLE OF COMPARISON, CALIBRATION AND METROLOGICAL CERTIFICATION IN ENTERPRISES //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 10. – C. 168-175.
- 14.**BADALOV N. J., RUSTAMOV N. T. THE ROLE OF MANAGEMENT IN ENTERPRISES THAT HAVE IMPLEMENTED A QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM //International Academic Research Journal Impact Factor 7.4. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 46-55.
- 15.**Badalov N. J. MANAGE PRODUCT QUALITY IN ENTERPRISES CONTENT //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION". – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 58-64.
- 16.**Jo‘raboevich B. N., Abduraxmonovich S. H. M. KORXONALARDA O ‘LCHASH VOSITALARNI SINOVDAN O ‘TKAZISHDA METROLOGIK XIZMATINING O ‘RNI //Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 701-704.
- 17.**BADALOV N. J. O. R. THE SIGNIFICANCE OF CERTIFICATION IN ENTERPRISES WITH A QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

//INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN
SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION". – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 2. – C. 146-156.